

Detecting Structural Transformations and Flares Activity in Binary Stars With a Cool Companion

Daniela Boneva

Space Research and Technology Institute, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Sofia, Bulgaria

Abstract

We investigate the flow's structure properties due to the mass transfer in binaries with a cool star. We study a possibility of activating flickerings and flares, in this kind of stars, in the result of dynamically unstable physical processes during the mass transfer between the components. A non-stable accretion disc configuration is then considerable. The relationship "flares - structure transformation" is established. We present a development of pattern formations throughout the binaries' connecting stream by the flow's fluctuations. We employ numerical computations and suggest a modeling of the flow's structure transformations. The observational data of two binaries are included into the calculations to analyse the quasi-periodic variability in the luminosity.

1 Introduction

In a vast population of binary stars, cool stars take an important place of the stars evolution study. Variability in brightness that could be appeared in a stochastic way on timescales of a few minutes with amplitude of a few 0.1 magnitudes is called flickering and has been detected in types of binaries that contain a compact object as a primary companion, including white dwarfs, cool dwarf stars and they are accreting material from a companion mass-donor star. The analytical study has been performed by Pearson et al. (2005) for the spectrum of flickering and flares. They have paid attention to the fact that the terms "flickering" and "flares" has been usually interchanged. In this reason they accepted for the "flickering" the events of the small amplitude, continuous variations and the term "flaring" for larger scale events. The idea about the small-scale fluctuations could arise as a result of instability in the accreting flow and a gas-dynamics source was proposed by (Osaki, 1989), who has investigated the superoutbursts of the SU UMa systems and suggested that tidal instabilities give rise to them.

Hameury and Lasota in (Hameury & Lasota, 2014) have turned down the possibilities the tidal instabilities to be the reason of the light anomalous. They found that the Z Cam behaviour is reproduced by assuming the time profile of the mass transfer rate from the secondary.

In Boneva & Kaygorodov (2016) we have studied the possibilities stream - pattern interaction, can result in low amplitude oscillations manifesting as irregular variations on the light curve of dwarf binaries. We have to also note that the casual low-magnitude variations on the light curve can also be a consequence of the presence of the density formation in the disc. Bruch (2000) has studied mechanisms generating the flickering. He proposes four possible mechanisms responsible for the observed variations in brightness: unstable mass transfer from the L1 point and interaction with the disc edge; dissipation of magnetic loops; turbulences in the accretion disc and unstable mass accretion onto the white dwarf. In Boneva et al. (2009) and Kononov et al. (2008) we have showed the relation between the flow's elements dynamics and the active state of CV stars. In the result of tidal interaction between the out-flowing matters from donor

through the point of libration L1 and the flow around the accretor, which have been studied by gas-dynamical analysis in (Bisikalo et al., 2003; Boyarchuk et al., 2002; Frank et al., 2002; Pringle, 1985, 1992), the conditions of the flow structure transformation in the close binary star system can be generated. In the current survey, we investigate the relationship between the disc's flow fluctuations and the flares activity, which has an effect on the light curve shape's behavior. We study the mechanisms that cause the accretion rate to increase and then to realize the transition from a quiescent to an active state. The results reveal the accumulation of mass, as well as the structure transformations, accompanied with the flows patterns formation that could be the reason for triggering of flares. We present the observational results of quasi-periodic variability in the luminosity of the studied binary stars systems with a cool companion.

2 Methods and models

We investigate a disc's configuration around the primary star after the mass transfer being started and as a result of interacting processes between the close components. In this case, it is necessary to include physical essence of the flow dynamics. The nature of this interaction allows employment of gas-dynamics equations presented in their applicable vector form, in (Boneva & Filipov, 2012; Boneva & Kaygorodov, 2016). The equations are as follows: The equation of mass conservation; the existence of viscous processes in the accretion flow, as well as influence of forces and rotation could be performed by the following Navier-Stokes equations; energy balance equation for a viscous non-ideal fluid; equation of state for compressible flow;

To define the conditions for further modeling, it is necessary to create discs structure models for cool stars type K. Based on the models of Merin and D'Alessio in Merin et al. (2004) we generate for two set with different parameters. They look like as in the Figures 1 and Figures 2.

In cool stars model we have a different temperature range and density, compared to the models of CV stars mentioned above. It is seen at the disc's models in section 2.1. Following the sequence of our physical model of burst activity in SS Cyg (Boneva et al., 2009), also its flickering version in (Boneva & Kaygorodov, 2016), we suggest here the similar stages of the flares development

in the cool binaries. In the result of tidal interaction in binary stars between out-flow from the donor star and the accretion flow, the flow could be disturbed. At some time, during the mass transfer, an instability and the resulting flow fluctuations develop in the disc. This leads to a considerable increase in the efficiency of angular momentum transport and an increase in the rate at which matter is accreted onto the white dwarf. The growing intensity of the radiation from the white dwarf inevitably results in heating of the nearest parts of the accretion disc, and hence to an increase of in the thickness of inner parts of the disc. The gas between the toroidal shell and the accretor experiences strong heating that leads to its expansion. However, the expansion cannot be isotropic, since it is restricted in the equatorial plane by the accretor surface and the inner surface of the toroidal shell, whereas expansion orthogonal to the disc's surface is impeded only by the accretor's gravitational field. The increased velocity of the heated gas will probably be comparable to the local sound speed, which is insufficient to form a collimated jet. The expanding gas can have a low angular velocity, and is prevented from falling on the star primarily by the gas-pressure gradient rather than by the centrifugal force. This enables the gas to leave the toroidal shell and form an expanding spherical shell around the accretor. The increased size of this shell can explain the stronger emission during the development of the outburst.

Further we apply the modeling on the gas-dynamical processes by the same numerical analysis, including codes and methods, described in detail in (Boneva & Filipov, 2012; Boneva & Kaygorodov, 2016): the Runge-Kutta (implicit part) method, Alternating direction implicit method (ADI), Centered-Time1Space(CTS)[forward or backward], Backward-Time1Space (BTS)[forward/backward], based on finite difference scheme or Godunov's algorithm. In the current study we are working again with "box-framed scheme", which we suggested in (Boneva & Filipov, 2012). Because of the different physical conditions (temperature and density values), established in the disc's models and therefore in a binary configuration as a whole, here we set some changes in the initial and boundary values of the parameters. We apply free boundary conditions at the outer disc edge, where the density is defined to be in a range: $\rho_{out} = 10^{-5}\rho_{L1}$, where ρ_{L1} is the density of the

Figure 1: Disc models for cool objects with different values of T_{eff} and R_{hole} (Inner radius of the disc). The plots show (Figs. 1a, 2a) changes in values of temperature, surface density, heights, ratios of heights over radius and the Rosseland mean opacity with variations of disc radius.

inner Lagrangian point L_1 .

3 Flow fluctuations and disc's dynamics

In the result of tidal interaction in a binary star between out-flow from the donor star and the accretion flow, the disturbances in the flow and mass tidal interaction give rise to the fluctuations in velocity and density. The physical essence of the flow dynamics responses to the interaction processes in binary. By applying the gas-dynamical numerical methods (see section 2) we have simulated the presence of two-dimensional wave patterns in the disc's flow. They are considered to

be an effective mechanism of angular momentum transport (Barranco & Marcus, 2005), what is responsible for the accretion rate's increase. The distribution of the patterns is more frequently observed along the outer sides, close to the disc's edges. According to the physical model above, when this kind of wave patterns leave the disc zone, they could fall apart and merge into the matter of the circumdisc halo, influenced by the conditions of low density there. We perform a series of runs with zero initial vorticity, but different from zero the initial turbulence values: $v(0) = v_0$, $\Psi_{r,\varphi}(t_0) = 0$, $\rho(t_0) = \rho_0 \approx 2.5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ kg/m}^{-3}$, $t_0 \approx 1$, and $r_0 \approx 1$.

Figure 2: Spectral Energy Distribution for two different values of T_{eff} (Temperature) and R_{hole} (The inner disc radius). In the plots we can see (Figs. 1b, 2b): The model flux in $ergs/cm^2/s^{-1}$ against wavelength in micron in thin black line. The model flux for the central star in dashed red line. It illustrates the emission from the star.

The wave patterns growth in r, φ plane of the disc zone. The box-frame values range from about $7.687 \times 10^{-15} AU$ to $6.68 \times 10^{-15} AU$ and from $7.687 \times 10^{-16} AU$ to $6.68 \times 10^{-16} AU$, corresponding to the above values of x and y , referred to as x_1 and y_1 . The results in stopover steps show the stages of the flow transformation. Firstly, a weak distortion of the flow laminarity is observed. In the next runs of calculations, the velocity values step to $(v(t_1, t_{n-1}) \approx v_0 + v_1)$ and the layers in the examined area undergo a weak undulation (Fig.3a). This means that the variations of velocity and density have an impact on the flow's behavior. For the final round of calculations the density and velocity accepted values $\rho(t_n), v(t_n)$ are used as an input. Then, we consider larger distortion of

the calm flowing (Fig. 3b).

The disturbed flow's conditions can provoke periodic or quasi-periodic oscillations, giving rise to the light curve variations. Since the density decreases with increasing radius, approaching to the outer edge, the observed luminosities must be correlated with the distance from the inner Lagrange point L1. In this way, the amplitude of light curve variations should be approximately corresponding to the density contrast.

4 Observational indications of flare-ups

In addition to the theoretical considerations above, we suggest some observational results, which demonstrate

Figure 3: Patterns formation in the disc flow, in 3D view. It is seen the laminarity break up and weakly undulations of the layers (a); the stage of stronger undulations and development of patterns in the flow (b). The light Blue and dark Blue colours show the difference in density in the interacting flow layers. The density values are increasing from dark to the light zone.

the existence of the brightness variability in binary stars. It is applied the data of V471Tau and V2436Cyg. The objects are binary systems with a cool star of spectral type K (SIMBAD objects and AAVSO data). The flares can be seen at the light curves of these two binaries. V471 Tau is a binary pre-cataclysmic system consisting of a cool white dwarf and main sequence star with an orbital period of 0.52 days. This is an eclipsing binary system and the change in brightness takes only 55 seconds (Hric & Kundra, 2011). The light curves of V471Tau show the typical flares behavior. For comparison, we create the light curve of V2436 Cyg (Fig.5), which is of BY

Draconis - type variable star.

Indications of active states can be also seen at the corresponding energy spectrum of V471 Tau (Fig. 4a, 4b) and V2438 Cyg (Fig. 5a, 5b). Swift-XRT light curves (created by Swift-XRT generator and explained in Evans et al. (2009)) detect flare-ups with small magnitude's variations. Energy spectrum, in PC mode, shows the most active part of the energy range. The count rates in the energy spectrum are active for the most part at low ranges. The observed Flux of V471 Tau at $(0.3-10\text{keV})$ is $3.6(+0.4, -0.4)10^{-12}\text{ergcm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$. The received spectrum of V2438 Cyg could not give us enough information

Figure 4: Light curve of binary with cool white dwarf V471 Tau (Fig. 4a). It is seen a flares activity at the time of observations. Fig. 4b shows the count rates in the energy spectrum, in PC and WT modes, are active for the most part at low ranges. (by Swift-XRT generator and Evans et al. (2009))

about the development of any flare-up conditions in this binary. In this reason we apply the data of the detailed light curve, which definitely confirms that the star shows activity during the time of observations.

In these two classes of binaries the different behavior of the flickering is detected. The difference could be caused by physical properties of the accreting flow, as well as by the dominating flickering mechanism or their orbital periods.

5 Summary

The results reveal flow structure transformation properties and their relation to the observational events as the quasi-periodic variability in the luminosity. It is shown the flow dynamics during the development even the weak flare's activity in the selected cool binaries. According to the light curves profiles, the presence of flares is detected at the above 2 binaries. Each of the events, which we have identified as flares, have a characteristic stellar flare profile. Stars eruptions are possibly related to the

formation of wave patterns and instabilities within the disc.

Acknowledgments

This work made use of data supplied by the UK Swift Science Data Centre at the University of Leicester.

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Figure 5: Registration of activity of V2438 Cyg light curves (Figs. 5a,5b). The small amplitudes of count rates show an appearance of flares during the short observational period. (by Swift-XRT generator and Evans et al. (2009))

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